

Consumer Satisfaction about Quality of Women Product in D-Mart & Reliance Smart in Nanded District

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Abstract:

Retailing has emerged as one of the fastest growing sectors in India. With organized retail chains like D-Mart and Reliance Smart significantly shaping consumer preferences. This study focuses on Consumer Satisfaction about Quality of Women Product in D-Mart & Reliance Smart in Nanded District. The research highlights factors such as women product. D-mart and Reliance smart have emerged as popular choices for urban as well as semi urban consumers' -Mart, founded by Avenue Supermarts Ltd., has built a reputation for providing essential women products like Apparel, Cosmetics, Accessories, Footwear etc.

Keyword: D-Mart, Reliance Smart, Apparel, Cosmetics, Accessories, Footwear, Need of the study.

Introduction:

The study enables the researcher to find out the overall satisfaction of consumers towards D-Mart and Reliance Smart in Nanded City. Organize retail stores has been increases, its converted into supermarkets or multi-brand stores like supermarkets, mall and hypermarkets. The researcher has been studied through pre-test questionnaire about consumer satisfaction of D-Mart and Reliance Smart services. There is need to study comparative analysis of supermarkets regarding their marketing and selling patterns as well as facilities and services which provided to consumers. The major focus of a middle class family is on the monthly budget which consists of various items Apparel, Cosmetics, Accessories, and footwear, food, grains, grocery, ready food and milk products, satisfaction of the family as a whole with reference to price and discount and offer is very important.

Objective:

The objective of this paper is to study the Consumer Satisfaction about Quality of Women Product in D-Mart & Reliance Smart in Nanded District.

Limitation:

This Study is geographically limited to Nanded district. This study is also limited to the D-Mart and Reliance Smart super Markets. Further the study limited to the Quality of Women Product for satisfaction of the Consumer.

Hypothesis:

The Quality of Women Product Items like Apparel, Cosmetics, Accessories, and footwear is one of the significant criteria of the consumer Satisfaction and there is significant difference between the opinions of consumer of D-Mart and consumer reliance Smart Regarding the Satisfaction about Quality of Women Product Items.

Sampling:

The Researcher has selected a sample of 250 consumer of D-Mart and Reliance Smart in Nanded. by using convenience sampling method. Their opinions are recorded by means of questionnaire about the Quality of Women Product Items and the Chi-square test was applied to the same.

Need For the study:

A study on Consumer Satisfaction for D-Mart and Reliance Smart is needed to understand differing consumer expectations. As D-Mart focuses on cost effectiveness and value, while reliance Smart emphasizes product variety and promotional offer to drive loyalty and competitive market positioning.

Introduction D-Mart:

D-Mart is the retail chain of super markets to serve wide variety of men and women apparels, food, beverages and other household products organized well-structured sections apart from that, fresh dairy products and daily need items along with baked goods for consumers convenience. D-mart also sells other household product that is consumed everyday by consumers. Such as e medicine and alcohol where is permitted. The huge scope of Indian retail market and potential to determine Indian retailer's giant by D-mart. Due the young generation preference towards lavish life style and demand for luxurious products along with increased disposal income shopping malls came into existence with pace.

Introduction Reliance Smart:

India retail sector has one of the emerging sectors to rapidly developed metro and small cities across the country. The consumers buying patterns shifted from convenience retail stores like Kirana shops to supermarkets. Reliance Smart is a grocery retain chain supermarkets to serve consumers need fulfillment. It is single brand of reliance retail which associated with Reliance Industries Limited. Reliance Smart is the one stop shopping destination which offering fresh grocery products, bakery, dairy products and vegetables etc. Reliance Smart incorporated in 2006, it is largest retail company in terms of revenue concern and 53rd rank in the list of top global retailers around the world. Reliance offer wide range of independence brands to Indian consumers with reasonable prices. The company has being operating supermarkets, hypermarkets, specialty stores, wholesale cash and carry convenience stores.

Consumer Satisfaction about Quality of Women Product in D-Mart & Reliance Smart:

This section presents the analysis of the opinions of sample customers regarding Satisfaction about Quality of women product.

Consumer Satisfaction about Quality of Women Apparel:

The researcher has studied the level of customer satisfaction with reference to Quality of Women' apparel. The results are shown in the following table.

Consumer Satisfaction about Quality of Women' Apparels:

Sr. No.	Satisfaction Level	Customer Respondents				Total
		D-Mart	%	Reliance SMART	%	
1	Excellent	61	24.40	97	38.80	158
2	Very High	89	35.60	74	29.60	163
3	High	74	29.60	54	21.60	128
4	Good	19	7.60	15	6.00	34
5	Average	7	2.80	10	4.00	17
	Total	250	100	250	100	500

It can be seen from the above table that, Out of the total 250 D-Mart Customers 61 (24.40%) have responded the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Apparel in D-Mart is 'Excellent', whereas, 89 (35.60%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Apparel in D-Mart is 'Very High', whereas that of 74 (29.60%) have opined the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Apparel in D-Mart is 'High', that of 19 (7.60%) have stated the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Apparel in D-Mart is 'Good' and 7 (2.80%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Apparel in D-Mart is 'Average'.

Out of the total 250 Reliance SMART Customers 97 (38.80%) have responded the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Apparel in D-Mart is 'Excellent', whereas, 74 (29.60%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Apparel in D-Mart is 'Very High', whereas that of 54 (21.60%) have opined the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Apparel in D-Mart is 'High', that of 15 (6.00%) have stated the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Apparel in D-Mart is 'Good' and 10 (4.00%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Apparel in D-Mart is 'Average'.

Thus it can be seen that, out of the total D-Mart Customer highest i.e. 35.60% have responded the Satisfaction level towards the Quality of Women' apparel is 'Very High' whereas, among the Reliance SMART Customers highest i.e. 38.80% have responded the satisfaction level towards Women' apparel is 'Excellent'.

Quality of Women' Cosmetics:

The researcher has studied the level of customer satisfaction with reference to Quality of Women' Cosmetics. The results are shown in the following table.

Consumer Satisfaction about Quality of Women' Cosmetics:

Sr. No.	Satisfaction Level	Customer Respondents				Total
		D-Mart	%	Reliance SMART	%	
1	Excellent	68	27.20	109	43.60	177
2	Very High	103	41.20	72	28.80	175
3	High	53	21.20	49	19.60	102
4	Good	17	6.80	13	5.20	30
5	Average	9	3.60	7	2.80	16
	Total	250	100	250	100	500

It can be seen from the above table that, Out of the total 250 D-Mart Customers 68 (27.20%) have responded the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Cosmetics in D-Mart is 'Excellent', whereas, 103 (41.20%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Cosmetics in D-Mart is 'Very High', whereas that of 53 (21.20%) have opined the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Cosmetics in D-Mart is 'High', that of 17 (6.80%) have stated the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Cosmetics in D-Mart is 'Good' and 9 (3.60%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Cosmetics in D-Mart is 'Average'. Out of the total 250 Reliance SMART Customers 109 (43.60%) have responded the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Cosmetics in D-Mart is 'Excellent', whereas, 72 (28.80%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Cosmetics in D-Mart is 'Very High', whereas that of 49 (19.60%) have opined the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Cosmetics in D-Mart is 'High', that of 13 (5.20%) have stated the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Cosmetics in D-Mart is 'Good' and 7 (2.80%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Cosmetics in D-Mart is 'Average'.

Thus it can be seen that, out of the total D-Mart Customer highest i.e. 41.20% have responded the Satisfaction level towards the Quality of Women' Cosmetics is 'Very High' whereas, among the Reliance SMART Customers highest i.e. 43.60% have responded the satisfaction level towards Women' Cosmetics is 'Excellent'.

Quality of Women' Accessories:

The researcher has studied the level of customer satisfaction with reference to Quality of Women' Accessories. The results are shown in the following table.

Consumer Satisfaction about Quality of Women' Accessories

Sr. No.	Satisfaction Level	Customer Respondents				Total
		D-Mart	%	Reliance SMART	%	
1	Excellent	66	26.40	111	44.40	177
2	Very High	107	42.80	71	28.40	178
3	High	57	22.80	38	15.20	95
4	Good	12	4.80	20	8.00	32
5	Average	8	3.20	10	4.00	18
	Total	250	100	250	100	500

It can be seen from the above table that, Out of the total 250 D-Mart Customers 66 (26.40%) have responded the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Accessories in D-Mart is 'Excellent', whereas, 107 (42.80%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Accessories in D-Mart is 'Very High', whereas that of 57 (22.80%) have opined the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Accessories in D-Mart is 'High', that of 12 (4.80%) have stated the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Accessories in D-Mart is 'Good' and 8 (3.20%) have expressed the Satisfaction level towards of Women' Accessories in D-Mart is 'Average'.

Out of the total 250 Reliance SMART Customers 111 (44.40%) have responded the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Accessories in D-Mart is 'Excellent', whereas, 71 (28.40%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Accessories in D-Mart is 'Very High', whereas that of 38 (15.20%) have opined the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Accessories in D-Mart is 'High', that of 20 (8.00%) have stated the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Accessories in D-Mart is 'Good' and 10 (4.00%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Accessories in D-Mart is 'Average'.

Thus it can be seen that, out of the total D-Mart Customer highest i.e. 42.80% have responded the satisfaction level towards the Quality of Women' Accessories is 'Very High' whereas, among the Reliance SMART Customers highest i.e. 44.40% have responded the satisfaction level towards Women' Accessories is 'Excellent'

Quality of Women' Footwear:

The researcher has studied the level of customer satisfaction with reference to Quality of Women' Footwear. The results are shown in the following table.

Consumer Satisfaction about Quality of Women' Footwear

Sr. No.	Satisfaction Level	Customer Respondents				Total
		D-Mart	%	Reliance SMART	%	
1	Excellent	67	26.80	108	43.20	175
2	Very High	110	44.00	82	32.80	192
3	High	51	20.40	36	14.40	87
4	Good	14	5.60	14	5.60	28
5	Average	8	3.20	10	4.00	18
	Total	250	100	250	100	500

It can be seen from the above table that, Out of the total 250 D-Mart Customers 67 (26.80%) have responded the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Footwear in D-Mart is 'Excellent', whereas, 110 (44.00%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Footwear in D-Mart is 'Very High', whereas that of 51 (20.40%) have opined the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Footwear in D-Mart is 'High', that of 14 (5.60%) have stated the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Footwear in D-Mart is 'Good' and 8 (3.20%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Footwear in D-Mart is 'Average'.

Out of the total 250 Reliance SMART Customers 108 (43.20%) have responded the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Footwear in D-Mart is 'Excellent', whereas, 82 (32.80%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Footwear in D-Mart is 'Very High', whereas that of 36 (14.40%) have opined the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Footwear in D-Mart is 'High', that of 14 (5.60%) have stated the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Footwear in D-Mart is 'Good' and 10 (4.00%) have expressed the satisfaction level towards Quality of Women' Footwear in D-Mart is 'Average'.

Thus it can be seen that, out of the total D-Mart Customer highest i.e. 44.00% have responded the satisfaction level towards the Quality of Women' Footwear is 'Very High' whereas, among the Reliance SMART Customers highest i.e. 43.20% have responded the satisfaction level towards Women' Footwear is 'Excellent'.

Summary of Satisfaction about Quality of Women Product:

The researcher has summarized the opinions of the sample customers of both D-Mart and Reliance SMART for the sake of application of Chi-Square Test. The results are shown in the following table.

Summary of Satisfaction about Quality of Women Product:

Sr. No.	Satisfaction Level	Customer Respondents				Total
		D-Mart	%	Reliance SMART	%	
1	Excellent	66	26.2	106	42.5	171.75
2	Very High	102	40.9	75	29.9	177
3	High	59	23.5	44	17.7	103
4	Good	16	6.2	16	6.2	31
5	Average	8	3.2	9	3.7	17.25
	Total	250	100	250	100	500

Application of Chi-Square Test:

The researcher has applied the Chi-Square Test to check whether there is any significant difference between the opinions of the sample customers of D-Mart and sample customers of Reliance SMART regarding the satisfaction about the Women segment.

Calculation of Chi-Square Test:

Sr. No.	O	E	O - E	(O - E) ²	□ ² Value
1	66	85.88	-20.38	415.14	4.83
2	102	88.50	13.75	189.06	2.14
3	59	51.50	7.25	52.56	1.02
4	16	15.50	0.00	0.00	0.00
5	8	8.63	-0.63	0.39	0.05
6	106	85.88	20.38	415.14	4.83
7	75	88.50	-13.75	189.06	2.14
8	44	51.50	-7.25	52.56	1.02

9	16	15.50	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	9	8.63	0.63	0.39	0.05
					16.07

Level of Significance 0.05%

Critical Value – 9.488 On the basis of above calculation of Chi-Square value the hypothesis are stated as follows

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference between the opinions of Customers of D-Mart and Customers of Reliance SMART regarding the Satisfaction about Women segment according to Quality.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): There is significant difference between the opinions of Customers of D-Mart and Customers of Reliance SMART regarding the Satisfaction about Women segment according to Quality.

As it is observed from the Chi-Square calculation that the calculated value of Chi-square at 0.05% level of significance and 4 degree of freedom is 16.07 and the Table Value is 9.488. As the calculated value of Chi-square is greater than the table value (16.07 > 9.488). Therefore the Null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

It is concluded that, there is significant difference between the opinions of Customers of D-Mart and Customers of Reliance SMART regarding the Satisfaction about Women segment according to Quality.

Conclusion:

1. It is concluded that, there is significant difference between the opinions of Customers of D-Mart and Customers of Reliance SMART regarding the Satisfaction about Women segment according to Quality.
2. It is concluded that, out of the total D-Mart Customer highest i.e. 37.60% have responded the satisfaction level towards the Brand of Women' apparel is 'Very High' whereas, among the Reliance SMART Customers highest i.e. 38.40% have responded the satisfaction level towards Women' apparel is 'Excellent'.
3. It is concluded that, out of the total D-Mart Customer highest i.e. 38.40% have responded the satisfaction level towards the Brand of Women' Cosmetics is 'Very High' whereas, among the Reliance SMART Customers highest i.e. 36.80% have responded the satisfaction level towards Women' Cosmetics is 'Excellent'.
4. It is concluded that, out of the total D-Mart Customer highest i.e. 41.60% have responded the satisfaction level towards the Brand of Women' Accessories is 'Very High' whereas, among the Reliance SMART Customers highest i.e. 43.60% have responded the satisfaction level towards Women' Accessories is 'Excellent'.
5. It is concluded that, out of the total D-Mart Customer highest i.e. 41.20% have responded the satisfaction level towards the Brand of Women' Footwear is 'Very High' whereas, among the Reliance SMART Customers highest i.e. 42.80% have responded the satisfaction level towards Women' Footwear is 'Excellent'.

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